

Pedagogical features of the development of sociocultural competence in the process of Rural Education

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ABSTRACT. The main purpose of the study is to determine the main features of the pedagogical aspects of sociocultural competence as an element of intercultural communication. Sociocultural competence involves the inclusion of students in intercultural communication, modeled in the classroom in rural education. The implementation of intercultural communication presupposes an adequate mutual understanding of communication participants who are representatives of different cultures. The development of psychological and pedagogical theory and practice has led to increased attention to the formation of sociocultural competence of students in the process of their professional training in rural education. The methodology includes a number of theoretical and research bibliographic methods. First of all, methods of analysis and synthesis of scientific and practical information were applied. The method of systematization and abstract-logical was also applied. As a result, the key aspects of sociocultural competence were identified as an element of the psychology of intercultural communication. Further development is needed on issues related to the formation of sociocultural competence in future students and the use of interdisciplinary connections in the process of their professional training in rural education.

Keywords: pedagogy, sociocultural competence, communication, psychology, education.

Rasgos pedagógicos del desarrollo de la competencia sociocultural en el proceso de educación rural

RESUMEN. El objetivo principal del estudio es determinar las principales características de los aspectos pedagógicos de la competencia sociocultural como elemento de la comunicación intercultural. La competencia sociocultural implica la inclusión de los estudiantes en la comunicación intercultural, modelada en el aula de la educación rural. La implementación de la comunicación intercultural presupone una adecuada comprensión mutua de los participantes de la comunicación, que son representantes de diferentes culturas. El desarrollo de la teoría y la práctica psicológica y pedagógica ha llevado a una mayor atención a la formación de competencias socioculturales de los estudiantes en el proceso de su formación profesional en la educación rural. La metodología de investigación implicó el uso de una serie de métodos teóricos modernos que hicieron posible lograr este objetivo. Como resultado, se identificaron los aspectos clave de la competencia sociocultural como un elemento de la psicología de la comunicación intercultural. Es necesario profundizar en temas relacionados con la formación de competencias socioculturales en los futuros estudiantes y el uso de conexiones interdisciplinarias en el proceso de su formación profesional en la educación rural.

Palabras clave: pedagogía, competencia sociocultural, comunicación, psicología, educación.

Aspectos pedagógicos do desenvolvimento da competência sociocultural no processo de educação do campo

RESUMO. O objetivo principal do estudo é determinar as principais características dos aspectos pedagógicos da competência sociocultural como elemento de comunicação intercultural. A competência sociocultural envolve a inclusão dos alunos na comunicação intercultural, modelada em sala de aula na educação do campo. A implementação da comunicação intercultural pressupõe a compreensão mútua adequada dos participantes da comunicação, que são representantes de diferentes culturas. O desenvolvimento da teoria e prática psicológica e pedagógica levou a uma maior atenção à formação da competência sociocultural dos alunos no processo de sua formação profissional na educação do campo. A metodologia da pesquisa envolveu o uso de uma série de métodos teóricos modernos que permitiram atingir esse objetivo. Como resultado, os aspectos-chave da competência sociocultural foram identificados como um elemento da psicologia da comunicação intercultural. É necessário um maior aprofundamento nas questões relacionadas à formação de competências socioculturais nos futuros alunos e no uso de conexões interdisciplinares no processo de sua formação profissional na educação do campo.

Palavras-chave: pedagogia, competência sociocultural, comunicação, psicologia, educação.

Introduction

Addressing the problem of forming the sociocultural competence of a future specialist is due to the general logic of the development of scientific ideas about modern rural education, its purpose, and its role in the life of a person and society. In the context of European integration processes covering various spheres of life, the need to adjust the goals of vocational education, which should have a sociocultural nature and form the appropriate competence of future specialists, is recognized.

To date, the issue of rural education is being studied by many scientists. For example, Stoddard, Toma, (2021) studied the features and problems of rural education in Poland. In particular, they highlight the following:

- weak technical base and lack of repair in many rural schools for many years;
- there are no special forms of advanced training, professional development and relevant methodological materials for rural teachers;
- schools do not carry out any extracurricular activities (often this is due to the fact that students live far from the place of study and parents do not agree to an increase in the load).

In addition, other scholars highlight the following problems of rural education (Dhaliwal & Bruno, 2021; Williams, Swain & Graham, 2021):

- technical education and informatics are not taught at a sufficiently high level (the situation is slightly improved by such central programs as "Internet in every commune" or "Inter - class", but so far Poland is in a disadvantageous situation compared to other European countries, in particular, the national average of the number of students using one computer);
- the modern model of general technical education has also not been introduced in many rural schools, although it could smooth out shortcomings in many areas of education. According to many, significant investments are needed, primarily in rural education. It is necessary to increase the flow of rural youth sent to vocational schools, and for this it is necessary to increase the level and quality of primary education provided in rural schools.

The professional activity of a modern specialist is multifunctional, the field is meaningful and international in its essence. It is increasingly becoming the scene of the interaction of a large number of factors, the interaction of people of different nationalities, peoples, the approval of diversified cooperation.

The psychological condition for the optimal functioning of a specialist in the system of professional sociocultural conditions is the achievement of a high level of sociocultural competence, which is considered as an attribute of professionalism. The structure, organization, and results of education and upbringing of modern youth put forward new requirements and tasks. The goal of the educational process at the university is the personal growth of the future specialist. The new social order in the field of education and the growing need for communication and cooperation between countries and people with different languages and cultural traditions require significant changes in the approach to teaching, updating the content and teaching methods. At the same time, there is a need to form the sociocultural competence of a future specialist in the process of studying at a higher educational institution.

A future specialist must be ready for intercultural communication, have a formed intercultural and transcultural consciousness to recognize the existence of another national-cultural identity, equal to his own culture. Sociocultural competence is a part of the general, psychological and professional culture of the individual, the mastering of which, in particular in the learning process, opens the way to the universalization of human qualities, contributes to a better understanding of one's purpose in the world, the formation of universal human values.

The main purpose of the study is to determine the main features of the pedagogical aspects of sociocultural competence as an element of intercultural communication.

Methodology

At different stages of work, a complex of methods of scientific pedagogical research was used: theoretical level: generalization of scientific information on the problem of research, educational, methodological and regulatory documentation; the method of theoretical analysis and synthesis to determine the goal, subject, research objectives, generalization of results using methods of scientific data processing.

Therefore, it should be noted that the application of the selected set of methods required a thorough analysis of scientific and practical literature, systematization of data and bibliographic information. By basic careful analysis and synthesis, we could become aware of a number of aspects, which will be presented later in the text. The abstract-logical method will allow you to better understand the material and draw appropriate conclusions based on the results of the study.

Research results

Preparation, professional activity, and the lifelong learning of a student is defined as obtaining competence-oriented knowledge, assimilation of values and socialization. The duty of the teacher's permanent activity in society entails the design of the tasks of the formation of competencies: taking into account the role of education in social mobility, professional activity in the conditions of multicultural liberal democracy at school, taking into account the problem of cultural tolerance, etc. Therefore, it is important to form a student's sociocultural competence.

Sociocultural competence has a structure that includes the following components: a) sociocultural knowledge (information about the country of the target language, spiritual values and cultural traditions, peculiarities of the national mentality); b) communication experience (choice of an acceptable communication style, correct interpretation of the phenomena of a foreign language culture); c) personal attitude to the facts of a foreign language culture (including the ability to resolve sociocultural conflicts during communication); d) possession of the methods of using the language - the correct use of socially marked linguistic units in a speech in various spheres of intercultural communication, susceptibility to the similarities and differences between native and foreign-language sociocultural phenomena.

Trends in the development of modern society, integration and globalization processes that lead to an increase in intercultural contacts, providing for the intensification of intercultural interaction, have led to a rethinking of the essence of cultural and national identity and the need for individuals to acquire relevant knowledge and skills in a multicultural environment. The professional competence of specialists in various fields of activity, both in the public and private sectors, becomes unthinkable without their possession of intercultural competence in order to effectively implement the goals and objectives in the professional sphere. Since the beginning of the study of intercultural communication in the 1950s and its introduction into the scientific field, the problem of intercultural competence has been relevant for all countries that had at least some contacts with representatives of other countries and could not reach mutual understanding. Thanks to the awareness of the cultural differences of various ethnic groups, influencing the formation of their worldview and the structure of countries, and further research of the factors that determined these differences, theoretical and practical assets of knowledge, skills and abilities that an individual should possess have appeared in the scientific world. achieving

success when interacting with representatives of other cultures Today, intercultural competence is a tool for achieving success in intercultural interaction and high-quality performance of their professional duties (Stadnichenko, 2021; Kryshtanovych, 2020; Lopes, 2019).

The formation of intercultural competence presupposes the readiness of the individual to interact with other systems of cultural orientation and is based on respect for other cultural values. Intercultural competence is the ability to recognize, respect and effectively use differences in the perception, thinking and behavior of one's own and another's culture in intercultural contacts.

Sociocultural competence is one of the components of communicative competence, which is a body of knowledge about the country of language being studied, national and cultural characteristics of the social and linguistic behavior of native speakers (Anwar, et. al., 2021; Bader, et. al., 2022; Abdullah, 2021).

In the 21st century, students require much more than traditional academic education, they must acquire a thorough knowledge of the use of technology for communication, and in the future, the ability to solve problems that are part of the tasks of social and emotional learning. At present, the formation of sociocultural competence is of particular importance, since the formation of social and sociocultural skills largely determines the success in future life.

The process of forming sociocultural competence encompasses a wide range of issues, among which the problem of preparing students for English-speaking interaction in a sociocultural context remains relevant. First of all, such training presupposes the formation of students' tolerance to other cultures, an understanding of traditions, habits, peculiarities of doing business, and national values. In addition, such knowledge contributes to the formation of a stable positive attitude towards foreign culture and the study of a foreign language among students (Baştaş & Aktunç, 2020; Diana, et al., 2021).

The formation of sociocultural competence will be successful when organized by the teacher and the students perform a number of specially designed and selected authentic exercises that will contribute to the formation of the following skills: to draw parallels between two cultures; characterize and evaluate sociocultural realities; know and understand the historical events of the country whose language is being studied; to form a positive attitude towards another culture; interpret sociocultural information in the formation of critical thinking skills; comment on foreign language material of sociocultural content; solve sociocultural problems in specially made communicative situations.

In the formation of sociocultural competence, the maximum objectivity of information, a comparative approach to the study of individual phenomena of the language, foreign communication between students and teachers can help. In the classroom, cross-language comparisons should be made, which will help in identifying the expressive capabilities of the native and foreign languages. All this will contribute to the emergence of a dialogue of cultures (Milkova, 2021; Santos, 2021; Usmanova, Khokhlova & Fedoseev, 2021).

All components of sociocultural competence are interconnected through the concept of cultural and social contexts, and mastering them should take place in an integrated manner. If the context of culture presupposes knowledge of realities common to the entire nation-carrier, then the social context is knowledge of the specific social conditions of communication adopted in the country whose language is being studied. So, sociocultural competence is the ability of a person to consciously take into account the knowledge of the social and cultural contexts of the country in the process of foreign language communication.

The use of the Internet, which is also an integral part of multimedia technologies, provides additional opportunities for searching for materials to expand the horizons of students and their sociocultural knowledge about the country whose language they are studying, in particular, using the global network, it is possible to freely communicate with native speakers of the playing language leading role in teaching a foreign language. Particularly useful Internet resources are electronic textbooks, reference materials (dictionaries, encyclopedias, databases); electronic libraries of authentic text, graphic, sound information, and video information; virtual museums, exhibitions, and other subject materials. It is multimedia technologies that are almost entirely related to the visual display of educational materials. As an example, we will cite such features of teaching using multimedia as showing video materials in English (documentaries and films), listening to English-language audio files (reports, interviews, songs), and using interactive computerized games to improve the memorization of the information received and check the formed English-speaking sociocultural knowledge of students. (Hernández, Sanchez, Zarate, Medina, Loli & Arevalo, 2019; Darovanets & Mishkoi, 2021; Kozlovskiy, et. al., 2021). All these tools, better than any others, help to form the foreign language sociocultural competence of students of higher education institutions in a short period of time.

Almost all changes and shifts in the higher education system are taking place with the help of Internet technologies, which are helping to transform the outdated way of learning

into a more flexible and interactive course for mastering knowledge. Today's Internet capabilities have a great influence on the effectiveness of education, because through their use, the teacher has the opportunity to introduce the latest teaching methods that improve the organization of the educational process as a whole. During training, the student can refer to the numerous available information sources in order to process the course material. Online training provides the use, in addition to text and graphic information, audio and video materials. Firstly, this variation of teaching information increases the interest of students in learning the language, because you can see and hear how speaking native speakers are in the information space. Secondly, audio and video recordings are visual material for teaching, contributing to the memorization and understanding of new knowledge by the student (Guillén-Chávez, Carcausto, Quispe-Cutipá, Mazzi-Huaycucho & Rengifo-Lozano, 2021). One of the decisive advantages of switching to information platforms when teaching a foreign language is that electronic technologies meet the requirements of the modern world and especially the younger generation. Indeed, for the successful realization of oneself in life, the student desperately needs mastery of modern technologies as a key competence. The rapid development of Internet technologies has become an incentive for transformations in the field of education, creating new requirements for representatives of society and the educational system itself.

Developmental psychology plays a leading role in the formation of the sociocultural competence of students because the study of a foreign language is based not only on the communicative aspect, that is, on the interlocutor, not only on the picture of the world, that is, on the consciousness but also the personality of the student.

The massive spread of web technologies in the everyday and educational environment has led to the importance of forming a new worldview of the educational system, searching for updated methods and forms of teaching, using social platforms in learning a foreign language. Simulation of life situations, work in teams to solve the set problems, situational analysis of tasks involve the use of information technology. The introduction of web resources in teaching a foreign language is a prerequisite for the present. The modern teaching methodology is a set of pedagogical tools that motivate students to explore various aspects of the language with a creative approach, form favorable circumstances for a holistic understanding of the material studied. Among other things, a significant emphasis is placed precisely on the formation of the sociocultural competence of students on the basis of authentic materials and the application of the knowledge gained in practice, that is, the transition from theoretical knowledge to practical skills.

Our study is important because rural education aims at comprehensive training of specialists — professionals in many areas who are able to correctly interpret and apply the law, understand from the position of law in all the subtleties of a particular life situation, make decisions guided solely by the letter and spirit of the law, realize their abilities and powers for the benefit of the individual, society, state. Therefore, rural education today, in the context of the modernization of the entire higher education, requires special close attention in order to identify a set of problems related to the quality of training of specialists, the organizational and content side of the teaching process, the financial condition of higher educational institutions, etc.

Discussions

Discussing the results of the study, it should be noted that the formation of students' sociocultural competence presupposes knowledge about the national and cultural characteristics of the country whose speech is being studied, about the norms of speech and non-speech behavior of its speakers, and the ability to build their behavior in accordance with these characteristics and norms. We believe that the formation of the sociocultural competence of future specialists should take place on the basis of their study, and classes in a foreign language, of the national culture of different countries of the world. Students should understand the difference between their native culture and other cultures, and acquire the ability to overcome sociocultural differences.

It is important to master not only the language but also the culture of communication, to know the peculiarities of speech and non-speech behavior of native speakers in certain communication situations. As a result, the main goal of the teacher in the classroom is to include elements of the linguistic culture of the people whose language is being studied into the content of education.

Considering the above, it can be argued that textbooks and teaching aid in a foreign language should include educational material (texts for reading and listening, sample dialogues, speech samples and formulas, educational and communicative situations, roles) for mastering models of communicative behavior in order to avoid culture shock and misunderstandings in communicating with native speakers of the relevant language, since, while abroad, specialists should be able to get a job in a hotel, consult a doctor, exchange currency, use public transport, shop at any supermarket, and eat in public catering

establishments. navigate international airports. That is why, when studying a foreign language, care should be taken to develop sociocultural competence in future specialists.

It should be noted that the teacher must constantly draw the students' attention to the realities of their own life, compare and contrast the traits of national character, moral principles, styles of behavior, the system of priorities in our country and the language of which is being studied. The effectiveness of the process of forming sociocultural competence can be ensured by maximizing the involvement of students in educational activities, which creates conditions for professionally oriented and intercultural communication. In training sessions, preference should be given to work in small groups, discussion, brainstorming, case method, simulation, presentation, dramatization, role-playing, business games, etc.

Conclusions

Consequently, the formation of a sociocultural component in students involves not only acquaintance with the history, traditions, habits of the country whose language is being studied, but, first of all, it should provide knowledge that can be useful directly in communication situations. Thus, sociocultural competence should act as the goal and result of preparing students for sociocultural interaction in the world and society. The foregoing allows us to conclude that one of the main goals of the learning process in higher education institutions should be the formation of sociocultural competence, which will help future specialists to take in society the place that most fully meets their needs and capabilities. I would like to emphasize the important role of sociocultural competence in psychology.

Certain problems of socio-cultural competence and intercultural communication in rural education indicate that in rural areas access to education is more limited than in the city: low material base of rural schools, a significantly lower level of teacher qualifications and the level of education of children, worse than urban schools methodological support of the educational process. Therefore, rural education in recent years cannot compete with urban education. The rural school requires active intervention and assistance from the scientific community in solving problems, interaction and cooperation with the city general education school.

An important contribution to the development of rural education based on the results of our study is the generalized information and the identification of the main elements of socio-cultural competence in intercultural communication. In modern education, the

problem of ensuring equal rights and equal access to quality education for all segments of the population, regardless of place of residence and social affiliation, is extremely acute. The problem of a general education school in rural areas is one of the most difficult in Ukrainian education, since the problem of the difference between the education of urban and rural students remains relevant today. The socio-cultural distribution of students into poor and rich, the low level of quality of life in the countryside have sharply reduced the starting opportunities for rural high school students in the implementation and implementation of life plans, made social benefits inaccessible to many of them, in particular, free higher education. All this and much more should be the object of study in future works.

As a result, through the use of modern theoretical methods of analysis, the key aspects of sociocultural competence were identified as an element of the psychology of intercultural communication. Further development is needed on issues related to the formation of sociocultural competence in future students and the use of interdisciplinary connections in the process of their professional training.

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